

The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the LGBTQIA community of Northeast India

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Abstract

The northeast region of India has been an isolated frontier yet strategically very important for the country. This article highlights the plight of the region's vulnerable LGBTQIA/LGBTQ+ community in the context of the outbreak of coronavirus pandemic. It gives an insight into the lives and struggles of LGBTQ+ persons and makes an attempt to highlight the impact it has had on their lives. Through some exemplary issues, it tries to showcase the level of vulnerabilities the pandemic has created that has only added fuel to the already burning community, that is, the community has been facing a horde of issues such as harassment, discrimination, and humiliation due to structural discrimination/ oppression and constant marginalisation in the society. These are socio-psycho distresses and they have been facing before the pandemic even started. It tries to explore if the challenges faced by the community are different from those faced by other vulnerable groups such as women, children, senior citizens, etc. It finally lays out some policies/suggestions that need to be taken up by the Indian government to protect and support the LGBTQ+ people.

Keywords: *Queer; Pandemic; Northeast India; LGBTQ+; Stigmatization*

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The region known as northeast India or simply, the NE, is a peripheral entity of the Union of India. It has always been considered a “peripheral frontier” of India. The region is a contested region marked by racial, ethnic, and linguistic diversity. Moreover, claims of contested ‘self-determinism and ‘integration’ have existed for a very long time. It also serves as a launch pad for India’s ambitious *Act East Policy* to integrate the region to the rest of Asia, particularly, with the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) countries. Within this ‘fringe’ region, there exist fringes whose social, political, economic, and cultural identities are shaped by various forces and regional structures from which they have been marginalized.

The Case for LGBTQIA/LGBTQ+

The pandemic has caused major disruptions in every person’s life. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic was felt by all groups and communities across the world. In India, the worst impacts have been faced by the poor, migrant wage-earners, lower-middle-class people, children, and senior adults. Millions lost their lives, and a billion suffered huge economic, financial, mental, and physical problems. Among the marginalized community who took unseen/unheard tons of the impact is the *LGBTQIA – Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex, Asexual/Ally* – community. The group is also known as *LGBTQ+*.

Least research and documentation has been done on the impact on this community. Media, including social media, have been relatively quiet when it comes to highlighting their plight - their survival strategy, migration pattern, violence inflicted, discrimination, alienation, etc. The community in this peripheral region, as happened in other parts of the country, faces huge challenges in their daily lives. Feelings of exclusion, hatred,

bullying, discrimination in public places are some of the common problems they often face. Even before the pandemic, many had to migrate to bigger cities to move on in life, whereas, those who could not afford to migrate continue to face poverty, joblessness, and other interconnected issues. These are the people whose legal identity has been consistently put into question in the Indian context. This is partly due to a largely conservative Indian society and, partly, due to India's historical legacy of a colonial state.

The onset of the pandemic along with its series of mandatory conforming rules and restrictions added an extra burden on their already difficult lives. Many who had migrated in the hope of finding better places to live have to come back to their previous places pushing them into further vulnerabilities. Apart from the economic collapse, the pandemic brought into a series of unusual experiences such as the mental health issue, shrinking space for community-solidarity, and also the scope for exhibiting their arts and expressions. The northeast region, being a less connected and isolated region, faces a huge shortage of essential items with the coronavirus outbreak. Shortage of utility items, a spike in hoarding, and the resultant rise in commodity prices led to massive panic situations in many states.

The old biases and stigmatization added fuel to the already burning community. The community has been facing a lot of issues such as targeted discrimination, harassments, and public humiliation due to structural discrimination and constant marginalisation in the society. In many cases, they don't get to stay with their families – the beginning of their ostracization process. Inability to cope up with the family pressure for 'sex reassignment surgery', they have to leave their home town for another city. This is a main reason for their shift to big cities such as Delhi, Bengaluru, and so on. This is not an uncommon thing in

the NE states. Hence, these issues did not just disappear with the outbreak.

The Impact of COVID-19 on the LGBTQIA community

Based on observations and conversations with the community members residing in the states of the region and listening to the webinar-talks of a few prominent faces among the queer and trans-community in the region, the impacts of the pandemic may be assessed and discussed as follows:

Impact on Mental Health

The issue of mental health got mainstream attention in many decades, perhaps, in a century all over the globe. The pandemic not only ravaged the livelihood of LGBTQIA people but also restricted their movements and expressions at a level they have never experienced in their lifetime. This has certainly affected the mental health of many queer and trans people. They are prone to fall into depression due to age-old non-acceptance by society and hence lack of support systems. The consequences are self-inflicting harm.

Lack of ‘mainstream’ support contributed to their indulgence in substance-abuse, drug-use, and even committing suicide. In many cases, stigmatization, cultural discrimination, and the group-members’ unconscious/conscious reluctance to share their true identity contributed to their lack of effective mental health care. Implicit preferences for heterosexual patients are pervasive. The mental issue face by the people of this community has been largely unaddressed. The issue is further aggravated by limited resources at their disposal to take care of their mental health. The most vulnerable among the fraternity are

those who have become homeless and are outcast by their own families. Moreover, disparities of affected people within the community in the region tell us more about varied policy and resource availability in different northeastern states of India.

Impact on Arts and Expressions

Attempts to express queers' perspective of life through creative representations have been historically misunderstood and often censored. Visual arts and artistic expressions on different platforms such as street arts, exhibitions, talks, and creative writings in e-zines and other platforms are some of their useful tools to express dissent, protest against scuttling their basic rights, making space for their 'radical' thoughts and worldview. They are potential means to showcase their originality, pride, and courage to stand up for their marginalized identities. The pandemic brought a temporary halt to their movements and artistic expressions. Many offline projects highlighting achievements in queer struggles in the northeast region, thereby eliciting responses and reactions from the fraternity and outside were halted. The pandemic has made them focus on daily survival issues rather than higher goals.

Impact on Migration

Moving into bigger cities of India provides many opportunities for LGBTQIA people of northeast India. The perks of collaborating businesses with like-minded people, being an active member of a relatively vibrant queer movement, the ability to have one's own space in the large city, etc. are some of the pull factors of migration. However, the avenues and opportunities come with opposite challenges such as racism, outward bullying, loneliness,

and so on. These challenges were made more vulnerable during the pandemic. The pandemic brought in extra issues such as racism against northerners. Outright harassment in public spaces as carriers of COVID-19 – a possible deduction from the ‘*Chinese virus*’ (Reja, 2021) tag used by the former American President is an example. Further, many LGTBQ+ people are uneducated. Many of them were deprived of systematic education at the early stage due to poverty and other inter-related problems. They were compelled to return to their original places due to the pandemic. On returning to their original home-states, losing of jobs and livelihood in these ‘*karmabhoomi*’, or the land where one works, cities were not compensated by warm welcome and support at home. Instead, they become part of the ‘procedures on arrival’ rigorous checks including scanning, selection, testing, and quarantining that often push their queer and trans identities into other levels of vulnerabilities (Bhandara, 2020). They were subjected to ‘migrant returnees’ attitude even within their families.

The Way Forward

While many people had the luxury to share quarantine pictures on social media with their families in bedrooms, kitchens, lawns, and living rooms, there were millions who could not afford to do so. Millions became jobless and homeless. Lakhs of migrant daily wage earners got exposed to the worst form vulnerabilities in their lives having no job to pick up for survival and having no one to take care of. The pandemic has instilled a fear-psychosis among the affected people. Isolation and loneliness have become the norm. For the LGBTQIA community, isolation and loneliness have been integral ingredients of their daily lives. The resilience they have inculcated along their extraordinary journeys,

simultaneously, may become their strongest weapon during the whole pandemic period.

In this context, the pertinent question asked by a famous queer activist, Kumam Davidson, could be re-visited. He asks, “*Must resilience be celebrated or must the system be reimaged and reshuffled?*” (Davidson, 2020). The LGBTQ+ people have suffered a lot for centuries. Their peripheral-ness in social settings has not been given adequate attention. The outbreak of the coronavirus has made their lives the most vulnerable among others. Taking a cue from the experiences gained from the pandemic, some community-specific measures by the state may be taken up.

- i. Protecting LGBTQIA persons from violence, discrimination, and stigmatization.
- ii. Involvement of LGBTQIA/queer organizations, bodies, etc. in developing a state response to any prohibited acts against the persons of the community.
- iii. Awareness campaigns and legal support for a comprehensive law for the protection and preservation of their rights.

Existing laws upholding the sexuality of transgender community has limitations. In a breakthrough verdict (*Navtej Singh Johar and Ors. v. Union of India*) in 2018, the Hon’ble Supreme Court had clearly stated that consensual homosexual intercourse between two consenting adults in India is legal and it should be applied without any discrimination. This was a positive change in the sense that the Court was bringing up sexuality and queerness in the public domain for discussion. However, the Parliament passed another controversial bill in 2019.

The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019, Kirpal said, “*is a very problematic as it does not allow self-*

determination of transgender status...does not offer reservations in public employment and education as had been directed by an earlier Supreme Court judgement...While the Constitution prohibits discrimination, that injunction only applies to the government and its instrumentalities. The private sector thus can discriminate with impunity in matters of employment, housing, health and education among other areas” (Kirpal, 2020).

According to Supreme Court Advocate, Saurabh Kirpal, India lacks a “comprehensive anti-discrimination code” to protect and preserve the rights of LGBT+ community. Although talks for such a comprehensive law are still an ongoing process, there appears to be a lack of political consensus for such laws in the country. Other issues of concern are the illegal status accorded to the choice made by a same-sex couple to adopt a child in India and that of same-sex marriage. These issues bring back the significance of the above point (iii), that is, the need for a comprehensive law to fully recognize and protect the rights of LGBTQ+ people in India.

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